

COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS AS A NEW BRANCH IN MODERN
LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article discusses the formation and historical background of cognitive linguistics. In this paper, we will discuss the factors of emergence, history, formation of cognitive linguistics and improvement issues. Scientific works in the field of cognitive linguistics are studied and theoretical knowledge is summarized.

Keywords: linguistics, cognitive linguistics, cognition, verbalization, conceptual structure, concept.

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive linguistics, which took its first steps in the last quarter of the last century has become one of the leading branches of linguistics at the beginning of the 21st century. The emergence of modern cognitive linguistics is connected with American scientists J. Miller, J. Bruner, J. Lakoff, R. Langaker, R. Jackendoff and others. Cognitive linguistics connects language with the theory of knowledge in the field of scientific research of its organic connection with social, cultural and linguistic phenomena, philosophy, psychological, biological and europsychological aspects of its formation. The word "cognitive" means "cognize, understand, understand" in English. Cognitive linguistics is a "cross-border science" that includes cognitology, cognitive psychology, arose in the collision of fields such as psycholinguistics and linguistics. In 1975, when the term "cognitive grammar" appeared in the article of J. Lakoff and S. Thompson. In the 80s, cognitive linguistics was established in traditional European linguistics. Russian linguist V.I. Gerasimov ("Новое в зарубежной лингвистике", 1988) entered with a scientific article. Another of Russian linguist E.S. Kubryakova gives the following opinion: "Cognitology is a multifaceted science. Linguistics formed in its framework, in turn, aims at the performance of complex tasks, relations

between linguistic and knowledge structures and constant analysis and explanation of alternatives is planned".¹

METHODS

According to Uzbek linguist Sh.S. Safarov, "Cognitive Linguistics task is to acquire and retain knowledge with the help of language, to apply the language in practice, and to transfer it, connecting the language system and structure in general with thinking as a reflection in the human brain, is deep scientific research."²

Professor A. Mamatov thinks about the cognitive analysis of the language system writes: "Cognitive science is cognitive if it deals with cognition. Linguistics is the study of the reflection and verbalization of cognition, that is, knowledge in language does. A cognitive approach to language is that the form of language is ultimately the human mind, thought is a reflection of cognitive structures. Cognition according to its structure systematization of all types of knowledge based on human cognitive activity represents."³

In addition, today the term "cognitivism" refers to:

- research program on human "thinking mechanism";
- processing processes of information coming to a person through various channels
- study;
- building mental models of the world;
- regulation of systems providing various cognitive actions;
- understanding of ideas expressed in natural language by a person and a computer program and forming;

¹ Кубрякова Е.С. О когнитивной лингвистики и семантики термина когнитивный // Вестник Воронежского государственного университета. – Воронеж, 2001.90-с

² Safarov Sh. S. Kognitiv tilshunoslik.-Jizzax: Sangzor,2006.- B.91

³ Mamatov A. E. Tilga kognitiv yondashuvning mohiyati nimada? Tilshunoslikning dolzarb masalalari: Prof. A.Nurmonov tavalludining 70 yilligiga bag'ishlab o'tkazilgan ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari.-Andijon,2012/-B.212-219.

- a computer program model capable of understanding and producing text create;
- a wide range of mental processes that serve mental actions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thus, one of the most important principles of cognitivism is the recognition of the individual action, controlled in mental activity according to schemes, programs, plans, strategies includes interpretation as a doer, active perceiver and producer of information. Cognitive science itself is a general science that controls mental processes in the human brain began to be seen as a science of principles. In addition, special literature from the perspective of cognitivism includes a number of disciplines - cognitive psychology, cultural anthropology, artificial intelligence modeling, philosophy, neuroscience, linguistics and others. In this regard, it is important to emphasize the interdisciplinary nature of cognitivism.

The main terms of cognitive linguistics: intelligence, knowledge, conceptualization, conceptual system, cognition, linguistic view of the world, cognitive basis, mental images, cognitive model, classification, verbalization, mentality, cultural constants, concept, world view, conceptosphere, national cultural space, etc. All these concepts related to the cognitive activity of a person, that is, as a result, a person makes a certain decision or comes to knowledge. Cognitive activity is accompanied by information processing refers to processes and consists in creating special structures of consciousness. Language (speech) activity is one of the types of cognitive activity.

CONCLUSION

Conceptual structure is the basis of the human cognitive system. Human cannot know oneself and the world without the process of conceptualization, conceptualization process includes two aspects of ability: one is abstract ability, and the other is and imagination. The external form of a conceptual system is language. of the concept has its own structure, but the existence and development of the concept of language closely related to its existence and development. The external world is

manifested as objects and their properties. The external world doesn't depend on the subjective knowledge of people, but the external world Description and description are inseparable from people's conceptual system. People always familiar to themselves in order to understand and recognize the beings in the external world they use concepts. Language form and meaning through conceptual structure establishes a mapping connection with the outside world. The system of knowledge is the totality of human cognitive experience. System of human knowledge classify the external world and recognize the beings in the external world, beings includes knowledge of qualities and knowledge of relationships between entities. The expression of a knowledge system cannot be separated from language, and the expression and understanding of language depends on the support of the knowledge system.

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